

Assessing the time difference of arrival and optimization techniques to determine strike location of lightning events occurring in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte

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Abstract — This work aims to define the optimal placement of a finite number of sensors to maximize the coverage area and lightning location performance in the Belo Horizonte region. The analysis evaluates the Least Squares (LS) approach to solve the non-linear Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) equations, using different sensor configurations and the Monte Carlo method. The impact of removing individual stations from the base case was evaluated, as well as the performance of network expansion. The results show that expanding from 5 to 7 sensors provides similar performance to expanding to 8 sensors, considering the available site options. Overall, the document presents a robust approach to determine the optimal sensor network configuration to improve the accuracy of lightning location in the Belo Horizonte area.

Keywords — time difference of arrival, time of arrival, lightning location systems, sensor placement network, Monte Carlo.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning location systems (LLS) are detection and mapping systems that provide important data on local lightning activity [1]. Depending on the frequency range of the deployed sensors, LLS can detect various processes and report features associated with lightning flashes, including cloud-to-ground (CG) return strokes, intra-cloud (IC) and initial continuing current (ICC) pulses, as well as the pinpoint location of the ground termination, the strokes' duration, and the estimated peak current.

These systems can be used to assess the lightning activity in a given region over a defined time interval, including the characterization of the ground flash density (N_g), which accounts for the amount of CG lightning flashes per square kilometer per year in a given region. This parameter is a crucial information for the design of lightning protection systems [2]

and it has applications across various fields, including meteorological agencies, aviation authorities, forest services, energy and utility providers, and other public utilities [3], [4].

The most common LLS utilize ground-based stations in which electromagnetic sensors are deployed. The data recorded by these sensors allows extracting a range of valuable information, including the location of the ground termination point for lightning flashes. To determine the precise ground termination location, LLSs employ various location techniques, the most prominent of which are Magnetic Direction Finding (MDF), Interferometry, and Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) [3], [4], [5], [6].

This work focuses on the study and the systematic application of the TDoA technique for a novel lightning detection network recently installed in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, Brazil. The goal is to understand how the number of stations and their two-dimensional spatial distribution influence the quality of lightning location estimates. To achieve this, the study first examines the impact of varying the arrangement of a fixed number of stations. It then investigates the effects of increasing the total number of stations. The evaluation utilizes the Monte Carlo method to assess the coverage quality and overall performance of the detection network sensors.

This text is structured as follows. After this brief introduction, a review of the main aspects of the application of TDoA technique for lightning location is presented in Section II. Section III summarizes the methodology deployed to assess the optimal features for the detection network configuration.

The main results are presented in Section IV, while Section V draws the main conclusions.

II. MAIN ASPECTS OF THE TIME DIFFERENCE OF ARRIVAL TECHNIQUE APPLIED TO LIGHTNING LOCATION SYSTEMS

The Time Difference of Arrival is a geolocation technique that utilizes the differences in the detection time of signals to localize and track emitting objects. In Lightning Location Systems, this technique enables the pinpoint estimation of the ground termination spots of cloud-to-ground lightning, based on the measured electromagnetic field produced during return strokes. Since the radiation field retains its distinctive signature as it propagates, the same feature (e.g., the initial peak) can be identified across multiple stations at different distances from the lightning flashes [2], [6].

This technique requires a minimum of three stations to perform localization. It relies on the time difference in the arrival of the signal from the source to the multiple receiving stations. This time difference produces a hyperbolic locus along which the source is located. By analyzing the intersection region generated by two or more of these hyperbolic loci, it becomes possible to determine the most likely ground termination point of the lightning strike.

From this perspective, the time difference of arrival between pairs of stations depends on the distance, D_n , between the emitting source (x, y) and the receiver (x_n, y_n) as well as the speed at which the signal travels (approximately equal to the speed of light in a vacuum, c). Considering a set of 3 stations, the lightning location can be determined solving this pair of non-linear equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t_{12} &= t_2 - t_1 = \frac{D_2}{c} - \frac{D_1}{c} \\ \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{(x_2 - x)^2 + (y_2 - y)^2} - \sqrt{(x_1 - x)^2 + (y_1 - y)^2} &= \Delta t_{12}c \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t_{13} &= t_3 - t_1 = \frac{D_3}{c} - \frac{D_1}{c} \\ \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{(x_3 - x)^2 + (y_3 - y)^2} - \sqrt{(x_1 - x)^2 + (y_1 - y)^2} &= \Delta t_{13}c \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

For lightning strikes occurring close to or within the network coverage, there is typically only one possible solution for the equations. Fig. 1a illustrates such an example, in which the three-station solution is sufficient to determine the correct location. However, in some cases, the hyperbola calculated from just two time differences of arrival can intersect at two different points, as illustrated in Fig. 1b, causing an ambiguous solution. In this scenario, data provided by additional stations can be used to improve the localization. To uniquely geolocate a lightning event using TDoA and provide information about time, latitude and longitude, at least four simultaneous sensor measurements are needed. Furthermore, mapping the altitude of lightning processes requires at least five simultaneous measurements.

Fig. 1 Hyperbolas, defined by the TOA differences. (a) Determination of lightning stroke location by three TOA receivers when the solution is unique. (b) Determination of lightning stroke location by three TOA receivers when the solution is not unique. Adapted from [7]

According to [4] the primary factors introducing timing errors on TDoA are variations in terrain elevation and propagation over finite conductivity soil, causing delays and attenuation of lightning electromagnetic signals. Additional factors include GPS errors, non-vertical lightning channels, and complex lightning electromagnetic waveforms. With more than three stations, noise in time of arrival data causes the hyperbolas not to intersect at a single point, resulting in a region of possible solutions in the TDoA method. Each of these possible solutions are associated with a pair of hyperbolas formed by the system.

Considering that n is the number of stations, the number q of hyperbolas that can be plotted is given by the combination C of $(n - 1)$ stations taken two at a time:

$$q = C_2^n = \frac{n!}{2!(n-2)!} \quad (3)$$

The total number of solutions that can be calculated is given by the sum of these two expressions:

$$q_1 = \frac{n \cdot C_2^{n-1}}{3} \quad (4)$$

$$q_2 = \frac{n!}{(n-4)! \cdot 8} \quad (5)$$

In equations 3 to 5, which were deduced mathematically, n is the number of stations; C_2^{n-1} stands for the combination of $(n - 1)$ stations taken two at a time; q_1 is the number of distinct solutions always taking a reference station in the construction of the nonlinear system (NLS); q_2 is the number of distinct solutions without taking a reference station in the construction of the NLS. For instance, using 8 stations, there could be 266 possible solutions that need to be evaluated. In this way, while using more stations in a TDoA systems improves the solution, it also increases the computational cost to analyze and optimize all the solutions. To address this, least squares (LS) approach is often used as an efficient way to solve the TDoA equations and estimate the optimal lightning location [8], [9].

III. APPLICATION OF A MONTE CARLO APPROACH FOR THE DETECTION SITES ASSESSMENT

The selected sites for the installation of the detection network sensors are indicated on the map illustrated in Fig. 2. The first station was installed at the Nova Gameleira Campus of the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), in Belo Horizonte. Four additional sensors were installed at different campuses of the Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG), all located in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, in the cities of Ribeirão das Neves, Betim, Sabará, and Ibirité. The proposed arrangement for the positioning of these 5 sensors considered the availability of secure and easily accessible areas for the field team, as well as the guarantee of good coverage of the urban area of Belo Horizonte. Stations coordinates are presented on Table I.

Fig. 2 Detection network sensors installed in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte. These sensor stations were strategically placed in Nova Gameleira, Ibirité, Sabará, Ribeirão das Neves, and Betim.

TABLE I
GEOGRAPHIC COORDINATES OF THE STATIONS

Station	Latitude	Longitude
Nova Gameleira (NVG)	-19.9384	-43.9990
Sabará (SAB)	-19.8695	-43.8390
Ibirité (IBI)	-20.0392	-44.0335
Ribeirão das Neves (NEV)	-19.7599	-44.0892
Betim (BET)	-19.9392	-44.1175

The performance of the lightning location network was evaluated using two metrics - one qualitative and one quantitative. These metrics were derived from Monte Carlo simulations, which comprise a computational technique that uses random sampling to obtain numerical results. In the context of this study, the Monte Carlo approach was used to generate 20,000 randomly simulated lightning strike events, which were then analyzed to assess the performance of the

lightning detection network. These 20,000 random strokes were simulated within a 50 km × 50 km grid (area centered around the Belo Horizonte region). The grid had density of 8 discharges/km². This parameter was chosen in order to ensure coverage across the entire Belo Horizonte region, optimize the computational cost, and achieve a lightning detection density similar to the N_g reported for Minas Gerais [10] and Belo Horizonte area [11].

Each of the simulated lightning strikes produces a Time-of-Arrival (ToA) response at each of the network stations, considering that they propagate without attenuation with the speed of light. To account for variations in terrain elevation, propagation over finite conductivity soil, GPS errors, and non-vertical lightning channels, a timing error was included on each ToA. This timing error was modelled as a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and a standard deviation of 1.5 microseconds.

This assumption considers a sensor network detection range of 40 km, and that the propagation velocity can vary from 0.99c to 1.0c. Works such as [12], [13], [14] quantify how the propagation velocity can vary and affect the location system. As described in [13], about 97% of lightning spherics have a propagation velocity varying from 0.985c to 1.00c. The timing error introduced in the velocity range of 0.99 to 1.00c represents a significant percentage of this data, which is consistent with findings from existing detection networks[15].

The second performance metric evaluated in this study was the distribution of location errors within a rectangle comprising the Belo Horizonte area, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Errors were categorized into less than 1 km, 1 to 2 km, 2 to 3 km, 3 to 4 km, 4 to 5 km, and greater than 5 km. The impact of individual stations on the overall detection network performance on this baseline scenario were analyzed through these Monte Carlo simulations. Furthermore, the potential expansion of the network to include other CEFET-MG and IFMG campuses within the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area was also considered.

Fig. 3 (a) Bounding box around the Belo Horizonte used to assess the location error distribution. (b) 20,000 lightning strike (LS) events were randomly simulated in a 50 km x 50 km grid, along with the detection network sensors. The bounded area represents the evaluation bounding box around the Belo Horizonte region, used to assess the location error distribution.

IV. RESULTS

The simulation results are presented in the following sections. The first part evaluates the impact of removing one of the existing stations on location performance. The second part

explores the effects of increasing the number of stations in the detection network. It is important to note that all simulations assume a strike within the considered area would be detected by all stations.

A. Impact of removing individual stations from the existing network sensors and placement evaluation

The impact of the remove any existing network sensor (BET, IBI, NEV, SAB, or NVG) on the overall performance of the network has been assessed. This was done to understand how the arrangement of a fixed number of stations influences the quality of lightning location estimates. The corresponding five Monte Carlo simulations are shown in Fig. 4, in which the station locations are represented by red squares, and a scatter plot with a color bar shows the location error, which saturates at 5 km.

Fig. 4 Monte Carlo Simulation for five different configurations with 4 sensors. Starting from the base scenario and excluding respectively each of the stations: BET, IBI, NEV, SAB and NVG. The red squares represent the sensor network and the scatter the calculated location. The color bar indicates the location error ranging from 0 to 5km.

Generally, strikes within the geometric area formed by the stations are located more accurately, while those outside feature larger localization errors. This behavior can be explained by the intersection of the hyperbolas used for locating the strike points. When the ground termination is located inside the network, the hyperbolas intersect at a small, nearly square angle, resulting in a tight, diamond-shaped region of location uncertainty and thus smaller errors. However, for strikes outside the network, the hyperbolas intersect at more parallel angles, creating an elongated region of location uncertainty as described in [15]. Additionally, for some configurations, a blind area is noted, which are regions where the employed optimization method cannot provide a mathematical solution.

From the Monte Carlo analysis, it is observed that the best results within the selected grid are for configurations that resemble a "Y" shape. For the 4 peripheral sensors, "wider" angles present a better response than "narrower" angles. Furthermore, it was observed that having a central sensor and the other 3 sensors on the periphery of the coverage area is a more optimal configuration than placing the four sensors around the periphery. Similar results were obtained when evaluating the Geometric Dilution of Precision for different sensors network arrangement [16], [17], [18], [19].

The distribution of location errors up to 5 km was also evaluated within a bounding box around the Belo Horizonte area, with the goal of quantitatively assessing the configuration that provides the best coverage within the Belo Horizonte region. The histogram and cumulative distribution function (CDF) plots of Fig. 5 depict the performance of the different configurations.

Fig. 5 (a) Error location distribution within a Bounding Box encompassing the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area, with errors saturating at 5 km (b) The cumulative distribution function for the 5 different configurations examined.

Regarding the percentages for errors less than 1 km in Fig. 5, the configuration without the BET station performed the best, with 54.68% of errors falling within this threshold. In contrast, the configuration without the NVG station had the poorest

performance, with only 23.58% of errors less than 1 km. This trend continues as is examined the higher distance thresholds.

For errors between 1-2 km, the configuration without the NEV station had the highest percentage at 28.12%, while the configuration without NVG was again the lowest at 18.68%. Similar patterns emerged in the 2-3 km, 3-4 km, and 4-5 km ranges, with the configurations performing quite differently. Notably, the configuration without the NVG station had the highest percentage of errors greater than 5 km at 31.11%, while the configuration without the NEV station had the lowest at just 5.49%.

These results clearly illustrate the significant impact that sensor placement can have on the overall location accuracy within the region of interest. Some configurations appear to provide much better coverage and performance than others. The data suggests that having a central sensor, and strategically placing additional sensors around it may have resulted in the best overall configuration for minimizing location errors in the Belo Horizonte area.

B. Impact of increasing the number of stations in the existing network sensors

Regarding a future expansion of the network, the influence of including new stations was evaluated. As a possibility, other campuses of CEFET and IFMG within the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, as well as the city of Nova Lima, were considered. The reason for including Nova Lima was that it was an area not being covered by any existing station. The main goal is to understand how localization accuracy improves with an increasing number of stations. To analyze the potential expansion, a series of simulations were conducted, varying the arrangement of the stations. Only the best configuration for each scenario with a given number of stations is presented in this study. The coordinates of the included stations are presented in Table 2.

TABLE III
GEOGRAPHIC COORDINATES OF SUGGESTED NEW STATIONS

Station	Latitude	Longitude
Contagem (CON)	-19.8737	-44.0437
Nova Lima (NVL)	-19.9918	-43.8529
Santa Luzia (STL)	-19.7942	-43.9137

The Monte Carlo results for four different configurations, with 5, 6, 7, and 8 stations are depicted on Fig. 6. Considering an expansion to 6 stations, the best configuration was found to be the base scenario with the addition of CON station. For the 7-station expansion, the best results were obtained by including NVL station. The addition of the eighth station did not yield significant further improvements.

The results presented in Fig 6 demonstrate that there is good location accuracy within the region formed by the stations. In contrast, the peripheral areas outside the network present more significant localization errors, consistent with the previous findings. As the number of stations increases, there is an

observed improvement in the coverage and location accuracy of the areas outside the detection network.

Fig. 6 Monte Carlo Simulation for 4 different configurations with 5, 6, 7 and sensors network. Starting from the base scenario and adding respectively each of the stations: CON, NVL and STL. The red squares represent the sensor network and the scatter the calculated location. There is also a color bar to indicate the location error that saturates at 5km

The error distribution for lightning strikes located within the bounding box of Belo Horizonte and the corresponding cumulative distribution function (CDF) are presented in Fig. 7. The data shows trend of improved localization accuracy with an increasing number of stations. The proportion of lightning strikes located with an error of less than 1 km increases significantly from 57.78% with 5 stations to 68.73% with 8 stations. This demonstrates that adding more stations substantially enhances the accuracy of the localization system.

There is a notable decrease in the percentages of localization errors within higher error ranges (more than 3 km) as more stations are included. For instance, errors exceeding 5 km decrease from 3.40% with 5 stations to 0.83% with 8 stations. This reduction is critical for applications requiring high accuracy. While each additional station improves accuracy, the most substantial gains are observed when the number of stations increases from 5 to 6 and from 6 to 7. The improvement from 7 to 8 stations, though still beneficial, shows diminishing returns, suggesting a potential point of optimal station density for cost-effective accuracy enhancement.

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) further supports these findings illustrating that increasing the number of stations leads to a higher probability of achieving lower localization errors. Additionally, increasing from 7 to 8 stations did not result in a significant change, as the curves are practically identical. In conclusion, this analysis underscores the importance of station density in achieving high localization precision, which is vital for effective environmental monitoring and risk management.

The results indicate that adding stations at CON and NVL yields the most significant improvements in accuracy. However,

the additional expansion to include the STL station may not provide an increase in cost-effectiveness.

Fig. 7 (a) Error location distribution within a Bounding Box encompassing the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area, with errors saturating at 5 km (b) The cumulative distribution function for the 4 different configurations examined.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results show how the placement of the sensors in the network can substantially impact the localization efficiency. For the configuration with 4 sensors, a better performance was observed for the Y-shaped network with a central sensor and additional ones around the perimeter. Considering the network expansion, it was observed that adding CON and NVL stations significantly increased the accuracy within the Belo Horizonte area, with the optimal configuration being to first expand to CON and then to NVL. It was also found that adding SVL would not bring significant improvement to the network's performance.

Based on the simulations, the optimal configuration for the Belo Horizonte network can be determined considering the available existing locations. Preliminary results demonstrate that the Monte Carlo simulations can be considered a good approach for studies related to the performance of TDoA technique for different network configurations.

Next steps of this study include the assessment of the real-time performance and operation of the implemented network. This would allow evaluating if the simulated results match the actual system behavior. It is also possible to investigate the

error associated with the measurements using real data, to propose specific corrections or improvements to the local sensor system, based on the insights gained from evaluating the real-world performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support and resources provided by the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG) for this research project. Additionally, the authors are grateful for the financial support received from the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG) through grant number PCE-00106-24.

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